

NOTES

Mixed Ligand Anionic Complexes of Cadmium(II)

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DIVALENT cadmium ion has a completely filled $4d^{10}$ non-bonding shell which causes least perturbation to the preferred tetrahedral stereochemistry ($5s$ $5p^3$). But with a judicious selection of ligands and under favourable experimental conditions, the coordination can be increased harnessing one, two or more number of $5d$ orbitals for bonding. In fact, we have been trying to synthesize cadmium(II) complexes exhibiting unusual coordination and with this objective in view we have earlier reported mixed ligand complexes of cadmium(II) dithiocarbamate with nitrogen donor ligands exhibiting coordination number five, six and seven¹. Some anionic complexes of zinc(II) and cadmium(II) exhibiting unusual coordination have also been reported earlier²⁻⁵. This communication describes the isolation and characterisation of a few more anionic complexes of cadmium(II) containing imidazole nucleus and isoquinoline as hetero ligands.

Experimental

Tetraethyl ammonium tri-iodo di-isoquinoline cadmate— $[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdI_3(IQ)_2]$ —

To a suspension of freshly prepared bis-tetraethyl ammonium tetraiodo cadmate(II) in methanol was added isoquinoline(IQ) in 1 : 4 molar ratio. No change took place immediately but on refluxing for 3 hours, a clear solution was obtained. On cooling overnight a shining needle-shaped crystalline

compound separated which was washed with methanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Tetraethyl ammonium tri-iodo mono-2-methyl imidazole cadmate(II)— $[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdI_3(2-M_2I_2)]$ —

2-Methyl imidazole ($2-M_2I_2$, .01 mole) in 5 ml of ethanol was added to tetraethyl ammonium iodide (.01 mole) in 5 ml of ethanol. The mixture was heated to a clear solution and was added to a hot solution of CdI_2 (.01 mole) in 3 ml of ethanol with vigorous stirring and was allowed to cool slowly. Micro-crystalline substance separated out which was filtered and washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Tetraethyl ammonium tri-bromo mono-2-methyl imidazole cadmate(II)—

Tetraethyl ammonium tri-bromo tri-imidazole cadmate(II)— $[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdBr_3(I_3)_3]$ were prepared as white crystalline compounds by the same method.

The metal and the halogens were estimated by following the standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with $\frac{M}{1000}$ solutions in acetone medium using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The analytical and conductance data are recorded in Table 1. The magnetic susceptibility measurements made at room temperature over solid specimens using Guoy method indicate that all the compounds are diamagnetic as expected for cadmium(II) ion with completely filled $4d$ shell. The infrared absorption spectra of the complexes

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM (II)

Compound	Colour and form	M.P. (°C)	Cd(%)		Halogen(%)		Δm (mhos) in Acetone
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
$[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdI_3(IQ)_2]$	White crystalline (needle-shaped)	148	12.9	12.7	49.1	49.2	222
$[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdI_3(2-M_2I_2)]$	White micro-crystalline	136	15.2	15.8	59.1	59.9	225
$[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdBr_3(2-M_2I_2)]$	White micro-crystalline	130	19.2	19.8	42.4	42.5	200
$[(C_2H_5)_4N][CdBr_3(I_3)_3]$	White micro-crystalline	118	16.5	16.3	84.7	84.9	140

both as Nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls were recorded in the region 5000-650 cm^{-1} using a Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics.

Results and Discussion

The imidazole nucleus and derivatives thereof are known to play extremely crucial role in the structure and functioning of a number of biologically important molecules, generally by virtue of their being coordinated to the metal ion. The interaction of imidazole with several metal ions has been studied⁴⁻⁶ and the coordination through the tertiary (pyridine) nitrogen has been confirmed by X-ray structural studies⁷. The complexes now reported behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes (Table 1).

The infrared spectral data are quite informative. The (N-H) bending and stretching frequencies of the free I_2 were observed at 1460 and 2935, 3255 cm^{-1} ⁸ and that of $2\text{M}_e\text{I}_2$ at 1458 and 2750 cm^{-1} respectively. In the spectrum of $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}][\text{CdBr}_3(\text{I}_2)_3]$, the $\delta(\text{N-H})$ is shifted to a lower frequency at 1422 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ is raised to 3100, 3300 and 3500 cm^{-1} . Similar observation of lowering of $\delta(\text{N-H})$ and raising of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ was noticed in case of the complex $[\text{Et}_3\text{N}][\text{CdBr}_3(2\text{-M}_e\text{-I}_2)]$. In the complex $[\text{Et}_3\text{N}][\text{CdI}_3(2\text{-M}_e\text{-I}_2)]$, while the $\nu(\text{N-H})$ band occurs in the higher range, the $\delta(\text{N-H})$ remained unchanged. In the complex $[\text{Et}_3\text{N}][\text{CdI}_3(\text{IQ})_3]$, the bands attributable to free isoquinoline, have been modified showing that it is bonded to the metal ion. Further the absorption bands at 800, 1010, 1065, 1180 cm^{-1} attributable to the tetraethyl ammonium cation are also observed in the infrared spectra of all the complexes.

Imidazole ($p^ka=7$) is less basic than its 2-methyl derivative ($p^ka=8.3$)^{9,10}. Hence an increase in coordination number is expected with I_2 compared to $2\text{-M}_e\text{I}_2$ which is substantiated in the present investigation (Table 1). When isoquinoline is used as a ligand, a penta-coordinated anionic $[\text{CdI}_3(\text{IQ})_2]^-$ complex is formed. Thus the preferred coordination number appears to be different with different ligands. In general, cadmium(II) ion in tetra-, penta- and hexa-coordinated complexes, uses respectively the $5s$ $5p^3$, $5s$ $5p^2$ $5d$ and $5s$ $5p^2$ $5d^2$ hybrid orbitals for bonding. Whilst the tetra- and hexa-coordinated complexes prefer tetrahedral and octahedral forms respectively, the geometry of the penta-coordinated one can be decided only by X-ray studies.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Mn(II) and Cd(II) Dithiocarbamates with Nitrogen Donors

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ZINC diethyl dithiocarbamate and other dithiocarbamates have been used as accelerators for vulcanising rubbers and as potential fungicides. Even though dithiocarbamates of Mn(III), Mn(II) and other divalent transition metals have been reported earlier, mixed ligand complexes containing both sulfur and nitrogen atoms have not been studied. In an earlier communication⁵ mixed ligand zinc(II) dithiocarbamate complexes have been reported. It was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation to the case of Cd(II) and Mn(II) dithiocarbamate and this communication describes a number of mixed ligand Mn(I) and Cd(II) dithiocarbamate complexes with nitrogen donors.

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade. Diethyl dithiocarbamates were prepared by earlier known³⁻⁴ methods. Mn(II) dithiocarbamate is susceptible to aerial oxidation. Hence this was immediately treated with absolute ethanol and amines in 1 : 2 ratio and refluxed for thirty minutes. Cd(II) dithiocarbamate was reacted in a similar manner. On cooling crystalline compounds were separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Metal and sulfur were estimated by standard methods and nitrogen by microanalysis. Conductance was measured in